

Structural elucidations in flavones using ^1H NMR 3-oxygenation shifts

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Abstract : A comparison of ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) of 3-acetoxyflavone with that of corresponding 3-deacetoxyflavone shows that the H-2' and H-6' of the both have comparable δ values. The observation is useful for structural studies in naturally occurring flavones.

Keywords : Flavones, ^1H NMR, oxygenation.

Introduction

It has been shown here that the presence of acetoxy group at C-3 in a flavone does not change the chemical shifts of H-2' and H-6'. This observation is helpful in ascertaining the presence of hydroxy group at C-3 in a naturally occurring flavones.

A comparison of ^1H NMR of 3,5-diacetoxy-7,8,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone (**1**) with that of 5-acetoxy-7,8,3',4'-tetramethoxyflavone (**27**) shows that in **1-27** : $\Delta\text{H-2}' = -0.04$ and $\Delta\text{H-6}' = -0.10$. The relevant ^1H NMR data has been given in Table 1, and the change of chemical shifts have been shown in Table 2. This comparison suggests that H-2' and H-6' are comparable in **1** and **27**.

The ^1H NMRs of 3,5-diacetoxy-7,8,3',4',5'-penta-methoxyflavone (**2**) and 6,7-diacetoxy-3',4',5'-trimethoxyflavone (**46**) depicts that in **2 - 46** : $\Delta\text{H-2}' = 0.01$ and $\Delta\text{H-6}' = 0.01$. This comparison hints that different substituents in the A-ring do not change the aforesaid trend.

The necessary conditions for making a comparison are : B-rings must have the same substituents; and C-ring of one compound should have OAc and that of another should have no substituent; as evident from the various comparisons made (Tables 1 and 2). Substituents for the two compounds under comparison may or may not be the same in the A-rings of the flavones.

A number of comparisons have been made in Table 2 and these support the conclusion that the chemical shifts of H-2' and H-6' remain almost unaltered in presence of acetoxy group at C-3.

There is a report of 3,5-dihydroxy-7,8,3',4',5'-pentamethoxyflavone (**47**)²¹, and the ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) of its diacetate (**48**)²¹ has δ 7.47 for H-2',6'. ^1H NMR 3-oxygenation shifts from **48** and 6,7-diacetoxy-3',4',5'-trimethoxyflavone (**46**) having δ 7.10 for H-2',6' (Table 1) are **48 - 46** : $\Delta\text{H-2}',6' = 0.37$, which are not negligible change of chemical shifts indicating structure **48**²¹ to be wrong. The structure **47** has indeed been revised to 5,7-dihydroxy-3,8,3',4',5'-pentamethoxyflavone (**49**)¹ and its diacetate is 5,7-diacetoxy-3,8,3',4',5'-pentamethoxyflavone (**50**). It is not in order to calculate change of chemical shifts from **48** and **46** because **48** is a wrong structure and it has been revised to **50**. It is clarified here that **48**²¹ (acetate of the natural sample) and **2**¹ (acetate of the synthetic sample) have different data and that is why the former stands revised to **50**.

The present paper deals with a hitherto unreported trend which is helpful for structural studies in naturally flavones. It is, however, pertinent to point out here that CMR is known to make a distinction between 3-oxygenated and 3-deoxygenated flavones; and δ values^{22,23} for C-3 in the two cases have been reported to be around 136 and 108 respectively.

Table 1. Literature data for chemical shift (δ , CDCl_3) of the protons H-3, H-2' and H-6' in flavones

Table-1 (contd.)

Substituents		Compd. Ref	H-3	H-2'	H-6'	3,7,8,3',4'	-	25 ⁸	-	7.70	7.68
OAc	OMe					5	6,7,4'	26 ⁹	6.30	7.70	7.70
3,5	7,8,3',4'	1 ¹	-	7.41	7.49	5	7,8,3',4'	27 ¹⁰	6.56	7.45	7.59
3,5	7,8,3',4',5'	2 ¹	-	7.11	7.11	5,6,4'	7	28 ¹¹	6.58	7.90	7.90
3,5	7,8,4'	3 ¹	-	7.84	7.84	5,7	6	29 ¹²	6.55	7.75	7.55
3,5,3'	7,8,4'	4 ¹	-	7.58	7.78	5,7	6,3',4'	30 ²	6.60	7.38	7.53
3,5,3',4'	6,7	5 ²	-	7.72	7.72	5,7,4'	6,3'	31 ¹³	6.59	7.38	7.44
3,5,3',4'	7,8	6 ¹	-	7.74	7.79	5,7,4'	6,3',5'	32 ¹⁴	6.58	7.06	7.06
3,5,4'	6,7	7 ¹	-	7.88	7.88	5,7,4'	8	33 ^{15,16}	6.68	7.97	7.97 ^a
3,5,4'	7,8	8 ¹	-	7.86	7.86	5,7,8	3',4',5'	34 ¹⁷	6.55	6.98	6.98
3,5,7	8,3',4'	10 ³	-	7.42	7.51	5,7,8	4'	35 ¹⁷	6.54	7.70	7.70
3,5,7	8,3',4',5'	11 ³	-	7.14	7.14	5,7,8,3',4'	-	36 ¹⁷	6.54	7.62	7.62
3,5,7	8,4'	12 ³	-	7.82	7.82	5,7,8,4'	-	37 ¹⁷	6.55	7.73	7.73
3,5,7,3'	8,4'	13 ³	-	7.52	7.70	5,8	7,3',4',5'	38 ¹⁷	6.49	7.98	6.98
3,5,7,3',4'	8	14 ³	-	7.69	7.70	5,8	7,4'	39 ¹⁷	6.47	7.69	7.69
3,5,7,4'	8	15 ³	-	7.82	7.82	5,8,3'	7,4'	40 ¹⁷	6.45	7.43	7.63
3,5,7,4'	8,3'	16 ³	-	7.43	7.46	5,8,3',4'	7	41 ¹⁷	6.49	7.62	7.62
3,5,7,4'	3',5'	17 ⁴	-	7.01	7.01	5,8,4'	7	42 ¹⁷	6.51	7.76	7.76
3,6,7,3',4'	5	18 ⁵	-	7.69	7.69	7	5,3',4'	43 ¹⁸	6.67	7.44	7.40
3,7	5,6	19 ⁶	-	7.76	7.76	7	6,3',4',5'	44 ¹⁹	6.70	7.05	7.05
3,7	5,8,3',4'	20 ⁷	-	7.48	7.57	7,4'	5,3'	45 ¹	6.69	7.43	7.48
3,7	5,8,3',4',5'	21 ⁷	-	7.18	7.18	6,7	3',4',5'	46 ²⁰	6.70	7.10	7.10
3,7	5,8,4'	22 ⁷	-	7.86	7.86						
3,7,3',4'	5,8	23 ⁷	-	7.75	7.75						
3,7,4'	5,8,3'	24 ⁷	-	7.55	7.55						

^a33 is revised structure¹⁶; previous structure¹⁵.

Table 2. ¹H NMR 3-oxygenation shifts (ΔH)^a in flavones

Compds.	ΔH-2'	ΔH-6'	Compds.	ΔH-2'	ΔH-6'
1-27 ^b	-0.04	-0.10	1-30	0.03	-0.04
1-43	-0.03	0.09	2-34	0.13	0.13
2-38	0.13	0.13	2-44	0.06	0.06
2-46	0.01	0.01	3-26	0.14	0.14
3-35	0.14	0.14	3-39	0.15	0.15
4-40	0.15	0.15	5-36	0.10	0.10
5-41	0.10	0.10	6-36	0.12	0.17
6-41	0.12	0.17	7-28	-0.02	-0.02
7-33	-0.09	-0.09	7-37	0.15	0.15
7-42	0.12	0.12	8-28	-0.04	-0.04
8-33	-0.11	-0.11	8-37	0.13	0.13
8-42	0.10	0.10	9-31	0.09	0.03
9-45	0.04	-0.01	10-27	-0.03	-0.08
10-30	0.04	-0.02	10-43	-0.02	0.11
11-34	0.16	0.16	11-38	0.16	0.16
11-44	0.09	0.09	11-46	0.04	0.04
12-26	0.12	0.12	12-35	0.12	0.12
12-39	0.13	0.13	13-40	0.09	0.07
14-36	0.07	0.08	14-41	0.07	0.08
16-28	-0.08	-0.08	15-33 ^b	-0.15	-0.15
15-37	0.09	0.09	15-43	0.06	0.06
16-31	0.05	0.05	16-45	0.00	-0.02
17-32	-0.05	-0.05	18-36	0.07	0.07
18-41	0.07	0.07	19-29	0.01	0.01
20-27	0.03	-0.02	20-30	0.10	0.04
20-43	0.04	0.17	21-34	0.20	0.20
21-38	0.20	0.20	21-44	0.13	0.13
21-46	0.08	0.08	22-26	0.16	0.16
22-35	0.16	0.16	22-39	0.17	0.17
23-36	0.13	0.13	23-41	0.13	0.13
24-31	0.17	0.11	24-45	0.12	0.07
25-36	0.08	0.06	25-41	0.08	0.06

^aΔH = δ values of the proton in 3-acetoxyflavone minus that of the corresponding proton in 3-deacetoxyflavone.

^bA- and B-rings are identical in the two compounds under comparison. In the remaining comparisons, A-rings have different substituents in the two compounds under comparison.

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